

Skills 4 eosc

- Skills for the European
- Open Science
- Commons

Supporting | eosc

 Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
 UK Research
and Innovation

Workshop Practice of informing Policy through Evidence

MS3.3 – Rome, January 30–31 2025

Authors

Elena Giglia, UNITO/T3.5

Betty Evangelinou, GRNET/WP3

Copyright

This work by Parties of the Skills4EOSC Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0.

Disclaimer

This Milestone 3.3 document is produced by the Skills4EOSC project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140].

The information and views set out in this document are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission guarantees the accuracy of the information included in this document. Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on the European Commission's behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

DOI link

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930637>

Index / Table of contents

Rationale and organization > 4

Achievements and feedback > 5

What we did on Day 1: theory > 9

What we did on Day 2: practice > 13

Rationale and organization

The workshop “Science4policy: bridging the gap between research and decision making” was organized within Task3.5 of the SKILLS4EOSC project, under the leadership of the University of Turin – Open Science Unit.

The workshop was a key component of WP3 dedicated to training on Science4policy, with a focus on researchers.

Communicating science effectively is becoming increasingly crucial in empowering society to take evidence-informed decisions to address its challenges, especially in the context of evidence-informed policymaking.

The workshop was intended to enhance researchers' communication skills and facilitate dialogue with policymakers by upskilling communication competencies.

To provide a complete overview, we scheduled a two-days pathway, starting from general theory on communicating science, then presenting the “science4policy” framework with more theory and a role play game, to culminate on day 2 with pure practice, engaging researchers in a session in front of a camera.

Participants had to send an application form, stating their interest in the topic, their experience in dealing with policy makers (if any) and their scientific background. Day 1 was open to anyone, whilst Day 2 was restricted to 20 people – who of course also attended Day1 –, to actively work in small groups, as specifically requested by the trainers. We had 31 participants from 9 countries. They were all researchers coming from different scientific backgrounds.

To select the trainers, we could leverage on the Brussels [High level conference Unlocking the Power of Science Communication in Research and Policy Making](#) organized by Science Europe in Brussels, March 2024, where we had the occasion to listen and appreciate their engaging talks.

Joana Lobo Antunes, Director of Communication at Instituto Superior Técnico Lisboa, was selected for her long standing expertise on science communication and outreach initiatives.

Alessandro Allegra, European Commission, brought his experience in understanding and shaping the interface between science, policy, and society in Europe, with a focus on scientific advice to policymaking.

Petra Buljević Zdjelarević and Marko Košiček, from the Ruđer Bošković Institute in Zagreb, are communication professionals with a recognized curriculum in broadcasting and social media management, alongside a collaboration with policy makers at national level.

The detailed programme and the extended biographies of the trainers are available on the [workshop website](#).

Achievements and feedback

The workshop was a success. All the participants shared their positive feedback at the end of the event, and the average satisfaction for the event resulting from the form we sent them is 4,67/5 for Day 1 and 4,73/5 for Day2. Besides the numbers, at the end of each day there was enthusiasm and pleasure in the atmosphere, and many people reached out to tell how inspiring and useful the event was. Many of them recognized that the event not only fulfilled but exceeded their expectations.

Not only did we have inspiring and captivating lessons – people stayed longer than the scheduled end to let the speaker finish–, but the trainers managed to create a really interactive, networked and participatory atmosphere, as was clear in the exchanges during the breaks, when everyone was engaged in conversation, in sharing experiences and in building bridges for future collaborations or initiatives.

The two theoretical sessions were perfectly complementary (details in the sections below). Even though the first lecture by Joana Lobo Antunes was supposed to be just an introduction on how and why communicate science, a participant defined it “a performance, more than a lecture”. Joana started with the importance of “showing what we are doing” to promote scientific culture, transparency, and inclusion – and to avoid stereotypes like the researcher as a middle aged white man closed in his laboratory. She also stressed how usually science is communicated in the

wrong way, showcasing only the “exceptional” result and not the long and difficult process to achieve it: it was clear during COVID, when everyone expected “answers”, whilst science is mainly about “questions”. Particularly appreciated were the examples of practical successful activities that can be replicated and/or be used as suggestions in different environments.

The second session of day 1 was crucial to set the scene on the science4policy framework, where science is the realm of facts, and policy the realm of values: that’s why it is not easy to put together people dealing with the world as it is and those with the world as it should be. The role play game proposed by Alessandro Allegra, based on the longer JRC version, was perfect to ground the theory and to show how difficult the intersection between researchers and policy makers is in terms of timing, different languages, different goals and approaches. Participants played enthusiastically as Ministers, policy advisors, researchers, advocates, to reach a political decision supported by scientific evidence.

Day 2 was dedicated to practice effective communication skills. Researchers were divided into four groups, each dealing with a controversial topic (depending on their scientific background).

Then four round tables were videotaped, in which participants played the role they choose for themselves; the choice was among the 4 characters proposed by Pielke, pure scientist, issue advocate, science arbiter and honest broker. Marko Košiček played a perfect “nasty” interviewer/chair – like it happens in real life – trying to divert, interrupt, provoke, and urge the participants. The videos were then shown and debriefed, first trying to guess the role each speaker intended to play, then assessing if they managed to get what they really wanted, and in the end considering if they were able to convey the main message they intended to. There was consensus on the usefulness of the practical session, as participants were guided to reflect on how the context can be disturbing, the interaction can divert you from you initial purpose or can also make you act differently from your initial intention (e.g. from a neutral science arbiter to an issue advocate once provoked by the interviewer). They received insights and tips and tricks on how to give an effective performance and communication in a round table, avoiding the pitfalls and the risks of a wrong tone, style, attitude.

What we did on Day 1: theory

Day 1 was intended to set the scene and give participants the theoretical basis for the practice of the following day.

Joana Lobo Antunes gave an inspiring lesson – someone in the feedback form defined it “a TED talk” – starting with a quote by sir Mark Walport, “Science is not finished until it’s communicated” and drawing a line among scholarly communication – peer to peer, scientists talking to scientists – and science communication, which is about scientists communicating to society.

She stressed that often science is communicated on newspapers or social media just as “breaking news”. Emphasizing only the brilliant results and not the process to get the results is a wrong approach: it’s like having only the final score of a football game without actually watching the game. Science is about the process, is about asking questions: the COVID pandemic was a litmus test, as everyone was looking for answers and researchers at the beginning had only

questions, and rightly so. But if the media habit is to highlight only the results, that's the expectation they create in the public.

Science communication, hence, is also about showing what actually the scientific process is and how research goes on.

She then tackled:

1. the reasons why every researcher should care about communicating science

Beside transparency and accountability, telling stories about research can help spread a research culture, can show that the "scientific method" can be used to create a critical attitude towards fake news and claim for verification of facts, and can help demolish the stereotype of researchers being only middle aged white men. It also increases the researchers' visibility and reputation. Open Science is of course functional to this approach.

From a selfish point of view, trying to explain the research you are familiar with to people outside your laboratory can be useful also to look at your data and finding with new eyes, from a different perspective, and getting feedback from "non-experts" can improve your research.

In the end, telling a story about your research also enhances the visibility of your original paper, hence there is also self-interest at stake.

2. how and why institutions should care and how they can help

If institutions see the value of science communication, they should set up a dedicated office to help researchers create media campaigns with the right timing and arguments. The office is not a secretary but a partner who co-creates and handcrafts the narrative and the tools to effective communication. Researchers should contact the office – they are not clairvoyants! they do not know about your amazing findings if you don't tell them – in advance as timeliness is crucial with the media.

Institutions can play a crucial role in supporting science communication by including it into the research assessment criteria, to incentivize researchers. Communicating science is still perceived as a tier-b activity, less "serious" or reputed than doing science itself. Again, it's a matter of cultural change that can be enabled by a different research evaluation.

3. how to catch attention and to be listened to

The first tip is to go where people are, i.e. social media, and start with a catchy message to grasp the audience's attention. Then researchers should use a comprehensible language – particularly appreciated was the initiative "Explain it to me as if I were 5 years old" conducted at the Técnico Lisboa – and create an appealing narrative. Two tips – among the many presented: use the "inverted pyramid" when talking science, i.e. start with the main message and then add details, as the attention span on social media is very limited; and use details to be remembered: "roses, not flowers" was a mantra the participants highlighted even in the feedback form.

Communicating effectively is not a given or a gift, researchers must be trained and institutions should be aware and supportive of that. Training is crucial at every level.

When Alessandro Allegra took the scene in the afternoon the floor was literally enthusiastic about the first session.

He introduced the concept of “science” as realm of facts and of “policy and politics” as that of values to argue about the difficulty of working at the intersection of the two in terms of language, targets, and time. Policy and politics are always a matter of “choices” and that’s where science can help taking “informed decisions”. He stressed the difference among “evidence informed” policy, in which scientists bring evidence but then the policy maker decides, and “evidence based” which is too mechanistic, delegates responsibility to the scientists, freeing up policy makers, and in the end overcomes the “compromise” step which in politics is the core.

As practical suggestions, Alessandro highlighted that evidence must be timely, credible, and relevant and presented the four roles of a scientist according to Pielke: the pure scientist, focused on their production and not able to engage with the floor; the science arbiter, who offers different options based on data; the issue advocate, presenting only one solution; and the honest broker, trying to convey different perspectives in a neutral way.

Participants were then invited to play the role game created by the European Commission JRC. They were divided into four groups acting as a Minister, a political advisor, a scientist, an advocate, in the country of Umland faced with the decision to keep on fracking to solve the oil shortage or not. Everyone appreciated the game, as it was clear that just providing scientific data is not enough, time is never enough, policy makers have no time and are distracted so the message must be concise and clear, and so on.

After the game participants asked to know more about the European Commission evidence-gathering process and Alessandro provided more insights.

All the slides will be available on the SKILLS4EOSC Zenodo community.

What we did on Day 2: practice

Day 2 was intended to practice what we learned on Day1, and, indeed, we started playing with a ice breaking game to show how difficult it is to “communicate”. Participants were invited to line up, all looking to the same direction, and to be absolutely silent. Then a drawing was shown to the first person, who only could mimic it in ten seconds to the next in line. The second person could pass the message only drawing, again in ten seconds, and so on to the end. From the first drawing which was a laboratory pipette, we got the verb “running away”.

The game was brilliant to highlight issues that often happen at the intersection of science and policy – or even in any communication scenario:

- when you are allowed a very limited amount of time, it’s difficult to convey the message
- when you are not allowed to give/take feedback, it’s difficult to adjust your message and let the recipients better understand
- having different backgrounds highly affects your understanding of the message
- any text (or drawing, as in the game) can be subject to different interpretations
- and, what is more relevant in the science4policy framework, there are many agents/intermediary people among the initial sender (the scientist) and the final recipient (the policy maker)

We then got again a bit of theory going through two use cases which made clear that the right choice of tools (e.g. a round table) or visual message (e.g. a photo) can help achieve the expected result.

The general tip was: try to be appealing, find a “hook” to get your stakeholder interested, and then adopt the “what’s in it for me” approach to get them engaged. As Joana Lobo Antunes reminded on Day 1, when you communicate it has to be “all about the audience, not you”.

After this setting, the core activity of the day started. Researchers were divided into four groups according to their scientific background; they were then invited to choose for themselves the role they want to perform (according to Pielke, as explained by Alessandro Allegra on Day 1) and prepare a 2 minute speech to be delivered in a round table.

Four rounds of mock up round tables were then video taped with professional camera and microphones like in a TV studio, and after lunch we had a two hour debrief session.

Each video was played and analyzed. We had an objective debrief, where the audience were invited to guess the role played and the message they manage to deliver, and a subjective analysis by each participant, to assess if they feel they achieved their goals and evaluate their performance.

Participants found the debrief very useful, as they could see themselves from a “technical” point of view and as in a mirror. The general impression was that it was difficult to perform the role they intended to as the pressure from the chair was huge, the time limited, the questions were not those expected and so on. Many participants noticed that even though they started intending to be a science arbiter (neutral) they became more an issue advocate (partial) as the discussion went on.

There are some common lessons learned here:

- the right attitude is “how can I make the most from this opportunity with this specific audience?”
- be concise, precise and tailored to the audience: you might not have a second round to convey your message, so don’t waste the first opportunity

- focus on the message you want to convey during the round table. Carefully prepare it and stick to the point, even though the chair or other participants steer the discussion in other directions
- preparation is crucial to have a list of arguments or points you want to be sure to convey; try to find “catchy” images or arguments to get attention and to be remembered
- rehearsing is also crucial; record yourself and replay the video to debrief and improve
- if you are representing an institution never fall into the trap of giving your “personal opinion” as there you are playing an official role
- be polite and reply to potentially nasty/provocative comments or questions “I see, but my point is...”. Do not be distracted by arguments or aggressive statements by the chair/other panelists
- never get defensive as in the end you get the opposite result and you can’t deliver your message; keep an “affirmative” attitude, be passionate but not aggressive
- your fellow panelists are people who can intellectually stimulate you, not “enemies”: if you look at them under this perspective, it’s easier not to be dragged in useless or aggressive arguments.

The activity was very much appreciated by the participants, as they reckoned in the feedback form: to wrap up, we take just two quotes, “I liked the atmosphere that the organiser created, it was very warm and welcoming. The workshop held a high level and the trainers created a secure safe environment to make us feel safe in taking part in the exercises” and “The variety of the group really enhanced the workshop. Different perspectives and strengths made the activities more engaging”.

www.skills4eosC.eu

in X zenodo

Supporting eosC

 Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
 UK Research
and Innovation

Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140].